

ISic0769

Honours for L. Naevius(?) Firminus Manilianus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (blue)

Object

tabula

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-08 - Jonathan Prag revised file based on work for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 23 September 1970, on the south side of room 6 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997854, 14.262475

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20227

Physical Description

Four joining fragments of a slab of blue-veined marble. The rear is finished smooth. The top and bottom of the stone are lost; the text appears to be preserved to its full width, but the left and right margins of the stone have been cut back, presumably for re-use.

Dimensions

Height 17.5 cm

Width 56 cm

Depth 1.5 cm

Layout

Remains of four lines of latin text are preserved: only the lower part of the first line survives, and only traces of the tops of letters remain from the beginning of line four.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are V-cut and generously (and sometimes unevenly) spaced, with moderate serifs. R is closed, and both A and R have lightly cut horizontals; all the strokes of M are off-vertical. Words are separated by comma-like interpuncts.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 65 mm

Line 2: 55 mm

Line 3: 43 mm

Line 4: incomplete mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1-2: 17-20 mm

Interlineation lines 2-3: 11-14 mm

Interlineation lines 3-4: 12-14 mm

Text

1. L̄(ucio) · Na[ev]iō · L̄(uci) ·
2. f(ilio) · Rom(ilia tribu) · Firmi
3. no · M[a]ni|iano
4. []

Apparatus

text from autopsy

Manganaro: Ti. Mevio

Translation (en)

(Set up for) Lucius Naevius Firminus Manilianus, son of Lucius, of the Romilia tribe [----]

Commentary

Scibona proposed reading the nomen Naevius in line 1 (the reading of Ti. Mevio... by Manganaro is not supported by the traces on the stone). As Prestianni Giallombardo has noted, the lacuna appears rather large for just two letters, but the text is notable at several points for being widely spaced (e.g. ROM and IRM in line 2, MAN in line 3) and the suggestion remains much the most plausible (Scibona's observation that one would expect to see the edge of the D if reading Nasidio is persuasive against this). The existence of a Naevius in the Romilia tribe at Sora (CIL 10 no.5742), noted by Scibona, does not by itself provide any necessary support to the suggestion; the Romilia tribe is not otherwise attested in Sicily (Prag 2010). Neither the stone nor the form of interpunct find immediate parallels in the other material from Halaesa. The form of the text and the double cognomen suggest that the text is probably of the second or early third century AD.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175723

EDR 075545

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